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EMPLOYEE ROLE IN SERVICE DESIGN-“A CRITICAL PARAMETER TO ORGANIZATION SUCCESS

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Abstract

This paper throws light on the “People “P of service Mix. Employees are the watchword in Service Marketing. It is necessary that relevant skill sets should be imbibed in the employees so that they have the crystal clear understanding of the service operations that can lead to ultimate customer satisfaction. Various organizations are dedicating their efforts through internal training & orientation sessions for the development of their employees with respect to expertise relevant for the effective delivery of the services. The ultimate goal of any organization is to provide service offering that can lead to customer delight. This paper will focus on the various Gaps of Gap Model and will suggest the various strategies to eliminate the customer Gap. Apart from that there has been attempt to understand which employee quality attributes are desired by the customers mostly.

Keywords: Service Design, Service Quality, Customer Gap

Introduction

Service design is the activity of planning and organizing people, infrastructure, communication and material components of a service in order to improve its quality and the interaction between service provider and customers. The purpose of service design methodologies is to design according to the needs of customers or participants, so that the service is user-friendly, competitive and relevant to the customers. The backbone of this process is to understand the behavior of the customers, their needs and motivations.

The importance of people in the marketing of services is captured in the people element of the services marketing mix, which is described as all of the human actor who play a part in the service delivery and thus influence the buyers perceptions: namely the firm's personnel, the customer and other customers in the service environment. Employees should ensure that they provide the service according to the customer driven standards in order to minimize the Gap. Apart from that they can ensure the following.

- Service organisations' need to be competitive
- Meeting customers' rising expectations of choice and quality
- making use of the technologies' revolution, that multiplies the possibilities for creating, delivering and consuming services
- Answering the pressing environmental, social and economic challenges to sustainability
- Fostering innovative social models and behaviours.
- Sharing knowledge & learning.

Gaps Model

The model shown in Figure 1 has some noteworthy features. Firstly it clearly separates the service provider from the recipient / customer / user. Secondly it identifies five clear gaps between ideal service and what is, in many cases, reality. Lastly it provides a useful and practical framework for considering

any service offering. Although not prescriptive in nature due to the wide differences in service offerings and the equally broad variation across time and providers as described above, it does offer a useful generic tool of analysis. Like all management tools, the usefulness is dictated by the skills and understanding of those applying the model.

Customer Gap

This is the focus of the model and in many respects the gap most providers should address first. It represents the difference between 'expected service' and 'perceived service'. There is a before and after scenario here in that expectations reflect the reference points customers / clients / users have before the service experience and perceptions reflect the service as it was delivered and received. Closing this gap could lead to better satisfaction and therefore a stronger long term relationship. Expectations are often difficult to quantify but exist on a scale from 'minimum tolerable expectations' at the bottom to 'ideal expectations or desires' at the top. The area between a customer's 'desired service' and 'adequate service' has been referred to as their 'zone of tolerance'. Understanding this zone is key as clients / users who are outside it are the ones who have a problem or an issue with standards being offered. Whilst it is not possible to have all clients / users within the zone of tolerance, it is important to know who is. Just as it is important to appreciate different clients / users have different zones, it is equally important to understand that different service dimensions have different zones. Finally, all zones may change over time. To close this gap, providers need to consider closing the following four gaps.

Gap 1

Gap 1 is interesting in that it highlights a problem faced by most service organisations but one that is not always addressed. It is that the service provider does not accurately know, understand or appreciate what their customer expects. All service employees should be charged with closing the resultant gap by changing or influencing service policies and procedures. The gap can exist because there is insufficient or no dialogue between providers and users. It can also exist because the organisation is unwilling to investigate expectations or address the issues that do emerge. Failure to understand expectations can lead to misuse of resources, e.g. investing in the physical environment or 'Servicescape' when it is not a customer priority.

There are a number of tools and techniques available that can be used to close this gap. Among the more traditional are surveys, complaint systems and customer panels. Providers might also wish to consider formal brainstorming sessions or gap analysis. Recent research undertaken by one of the authors' team (Gray et al, 2001) into service sector competitiveness revealed that top performing firms benchmarked themselves against successful companies in a completely different industry.

The problem is exacerbated by the fact that not all clients / users are the same and therefore have different requirements, expectations and needs. Better understanding these various segments can lead to a more efficient use of resources and greater satisfaction. Zazelenchuk and Boling (2003) report on a usability evaluation survey that was conducted in 2001 on the Indiana University's OneStart portal. Users were asked to rate their satisfaction with the system and also to explain their rationale for rating it the way they did. The most frequently mentioned was 'perceived utility or usefulness'. Portal technology can be leveraged to offer mass customisation.

Gap 2

Gap two is the difference between a service providers' perception of clients / users expectations and the subsequent development of customer-driven designs and standards. It is not enough to simply understand clients / users perceptions, that knowledge must translate itself to meaningful service offerings at an appropriate level or to an appropriate standard. The gap may exist because the personnel responsible for determining and setting standards are of the opinion that clients / users expectations are unrealistic or unreasonable. Additionally they believe that the heterogeneity of services means that setting

standards is fraught with difficulty and therefore of less importance. Service excellence remains a challenge for most organisations and the quality of service delivered is a function of the standards set by management.

Gap 3

This is the gap between the service designs and standards and actual service delivery. In other words having guidelines, manuals and well-communicated standards is not enough to guarantee excellent service. Resources in the form of people, systems and appropriate technology also need to be in place and adequately monitored. Contact personnel must be properly trained, motivated, measured and compensated according to service delivery standards. Thus, successful implementation of service standards that adequately reflect clients / users expectations is meaningless if the quality of delivery falls short. Ensuring that adequate resources are available is the only way the gap can be narrowed. Add the uncontrollable factor of customer heterogeneity and the problem intensifies. Customers are guilty of not performing their role properly in the service exchange, e.g. not accurately specifying their requirements. They can also impact negatively on the service experience of others. Lastly there is a need to better control and synchronise supply and demand as peak demand periods can unfairly lead to customer dissatisfaction.

There are a number of HR strategies for closing gap three and these are shown in Figure 2. These strategies are beyond the scope of this paper but will be expanded upon during the conference presentation.

The following are the strategies for elimination of GAP3

A survey was conducted at one of the customer care center of Idea in Kanpur. The customers were required to fill the questionnaire and they gave their responses for the various employee qualities.

Employee Quality dimension	Priority by customer in %
Reliability	60%
Technical competence	15%
Responsiveness	20%
Empathy	5%

Conclusions:

- 1) The employees should focus on “Reliability” i.e. building block of service quality.
- 2) The companies should impart technical knowledge also to the sales staff in case of technical products so that they can handle service operations as well as installations.
- 3) Focus on the service triangle (comprising of Internal, Interactive and External marketing) to reap the benefits to everyone across the periphery.
- 4) The service providers can act as trusted advisors to customers if they can handle their roles effectively.

References:

- 1) Christopher Lovelock and Jochen Wirtz (2011), Services Marketing – People, Technology, Strategy. 7th ed., Upper Saddle River, New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
- 2) Marketing Management: A South Asian Perspective, 13th Edition, Philip Kotler, Kelvin Lane Keller, Abraham Koshy, Mithileshwar Jha, Pearson Publications.
- 3) Bowman, Peter (2012). "Service 7", Short Stop Press. www.service7.com.au